

Systematic Review: Post-conflict Peacebuilding Literature and Methodological Challenges

Muhammad Sazzad Hossain Siddiqui
University of Dhaka
Anthony J Lynch
University of New England
Bertram A Jenkins
University of New England

ABSTRACT: In recent decades, there has been increased policy attention and research interest in post-conflict environments across the humanities, arts, and social science disciplines. Our article aims to provide a methodological procedure that offers a nuanced understanding of recent peacebuilding scholarships and methodological challenges from a transdisciplinary perspective. The findings of our literature review indicate that the relationship between post-conflict peacebuilding interventions and the resulting liberal/hybrid peace is complex and intricate. This review highlights the significance of locally-engrained indigenous peace in this context of the Chittagong Hill Tracts in Bangladesh, which is the focus of the study. We conclude that in depth research and analysis are necessary to explore the underlying causes of local indigenous hostility and the potential for locally-engrained endogenous peace, which involves a reasoned approach to governing specific communities. We propose in this paper a justified and practical systematic review procedure, with necessary adaptations, along with multiple research implications. This procedure will be valuable to future researchers in humanities, social sciences, and behavioural sciences, as it encourages them to ensure a more focused and rigorous approach to the choice of literature selection for their research, providing a solid foundation for researchers to follow.

Keywords: Post-conflict peacebuilding, systematic review, endogenous peace, methodological challenges, Liberal/hybrid peace

Introduction

Rationales for Choosing the CHT

Background of Systematic Review and its Importance

Indigeneity, Peace Infrastructure, Positive Peace, and Hybrid Peace

Findings and Discussion

Methods, Gaps and Cases Underpinned in the Reviewed Articles

Conclusion

References

Author Contact

1. Introduction

Conflict-ravaged settings receive immense amounts of development assistance spent mostly on post-conflict reconstruction programs commonly known as peacebuilding. Peacebuilding refers to a comprehensive and long-term process that aims to address root causes of conflict, promote reconciliation, and establish sustainable peace in societies that have experienced violence or political instability. Peacebuilding includes various activities

and interventions that focus on fostering dialogue, promoting justice, addressing socio-economic inequalities, building trust, and strengthening institutions to prevent the recurrence of violence and facilitate the healing and transformation of communities. In 2017, for instance, the UN Secretariat spent around US \$1 billion on prevention, mediation and peacebuilding (Boutellis, 2017). Despite the large amounts of funding, most such efforts have proved unsuccessful in resolving underlying factors that led to conflict (Campbell, Chandler, & Sabaratnam, 2011; Chandler, 2014b; Duffield, 2014). The quest for 'liberal peace' has seen local culture contexts marginalized in pursuit of the often Western-oriented 'universal ideal,' thereby downplaying or ignoring the complexities of the context in which post-conflict peacebuilding takes place (Richmond, 2009; T Call & de Coning, 2017; Werner, 2010).

Over the past decade, following setbacks in many conflict-ravaged environments, as in Burundi and South Sudan (De Coning, 2018), international peacebuilding has moved on everywhere from being an obsessive hegemonic focus on traditional liberal peace, towards a concern for peace hybridity, interactions between local historic traditions and international liberal ideals (Richmond, 2009; Roberts, 2008). Still, while such talk of hybridity aims (or claims) to overcome a hegemonic focality, in the end, as we demonstrate in our case study, it amounts to little more than a piece of jargon drawn from biology, and from conjectured examples that do not stand up to scrutiny. Why, do peacebuilding attempts often fail, and we see a return to armed violence? What would it take to bring positive, effective, and enduring peace to those areas? Peace researchers and practitioners have been exploring these questions for decades, driven by, and rendered intractable by, a general reliance on a one-size-fits-all model wherein the peace workers, international actors, civil society and nongovernmental organizations pay very little attention to the historical and cultural concerns of the conflict affected contexts (Werner, 2010). The 2015 reviews of the UN have since backed away from this one-size-fits-all model and recommends broadening inclusion with improved local leadership and promoting coherence at the intergovernmental levels (Rosenthal, 2015).

In setting out to further our understanding of the peacebuilding literature and its development(s) this paper critically interrogates literature utilizing a systematic review protocol (Gough, Oliver, & Thomas, 2017; Petticrew & Roberts, 2008; Wright, Brand, Dunn, & Spindler, 2007) that enables us to isolate factors that may lead to peacebuilding failure. The practical, policy outcome of this is to be able to recommend context-specific peace intervention – for a locally-ingrained endogenous version of peace – through a process of decolonization of both peace and peacebuilding from its hegemonic embodying 'liberal' and 'hybrid' guises. At the very least, we argue, doing this helps us to see what is going on with more recent talk of the emerging sustaining peace proposition (De Coning, 2016; Mahmoud & Makoond, 2017); local infrastructures for peace (Richmond, 2013); and the "adaptive peacebuilding" of De Coning (2018). In accordance with the guiding principles of a systematic review, which prioritize critical appraisal and synthesis of current scholarly works and their respective findings (Armstrong, Hall, Doyle, & Waters, 2011), our study focuses on the examination of academic literature published as journal articles. Specifically, we aim to analyse how this literature, consisting of a shortlist of 43 articles, addresses the issue of peacebuilding in post-conflict perspectives. We have applied the knowledge and information

gleaned from the literature to examine peacebuilding in the Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT) as explained in detail below. The following (Figure I) was produced utilizing NVivo12 software word cloud's frequency query option. At this crude level of analysis, the centrality of liberal peace, and the emerging relationships between liberal and hybrid, the local and international, are conspicuous.

Figure I. Representativeness of the study themes

With his background in place, our inquiry addresses the following questions:

Q1. What are the scientific – i.e., refereed journal articles – in the peacebuilding literature especially related to peace infrastructure, positive peace, and indigeneity, and how well do they explain the post-liberal hybrid peacebuilding?

Q2. What are the current trends in post-conflict peacebuilding research, theories, methods, and themes?

Q3. To what extent has the hybrid peace concept been used in those selected studies including, the special focus of this study, Bangladesh's post-Accord Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT)?

Q4. What are the knowledge gaps in, and what are the methodological challenges associated with this literature?

2. Rationales for Choosing the CHT

The Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT) conflict is a long-standing conflict centered in the southeastern region of Bangladesh, primarily involving the indigenous communities of the area. Its origins can be traced back to the era of British colonial rule in the Indian subcontinent when the CHT maintained its distinct cultural identity. However, with the partition of India in 1947 and the formation of Pakistan, the CHT came under Pakistani administration. Tensions between the indigenous communities and the state escalated in the 1960s due to the introduction of land and forest policies that marginalized the

indigenous population and allowed outsiders to seize their land (Roy, 2000). These policies posed threats to the cultural identity and land rights of the indigenous communities, resulting in growing discontent and resentment. Following Bangladesh's independence from Pakistan in 1971, the newly established Bangladeshi state sought to exert control over the CHT. This led to intensified conflicts between the military and indigenous guerrilla groups, predominantly the Shanti Bahini (Peace Force), who took up arms to fight for autonomy and self-determination (Panday and Jamil, 2009). The conflict reached its peak in the 1980s and early 1990s, marked by violent clashes and human rights abuses perpetrated by both sides. The military conducted extensive operations in the region, leading to displacement, loss of life, and the destruction of villages (Levene, 1999).

In 1997, after years of negotiations, the Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord was signed between the government of Bangladesh and indigenous representatives. However, the post-accord peacebuilding implementation has faced challenges, with ongoing issues related to land rights, rehabilitation, and political representation (Partha, 2020). While efforts have been taken to resolve the prevailing problems, the CHT conflict remains a complex and ongoing issue due to non-local development projects, the imposition of infrastructure initiatives from outside the CHT, instead of prioritizing cultural preservation, land rights, and political representation of the indigenous peoples (Badiuzzaman and Murshed, 2015). The CHT case study is important to examine due to its unique socio-political context, the high cost of ethnic conflict, the potential for peacebuilding lessons, its relevance to similar conflicts in the global south, e.g., Mindanao, and opportunities for international collaboration to prevent similar problems from arising to undermine expensive peacebuilding efforts. Understanding and addressing the complexities of the CHT conflict contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of conflicts involving minority indigenous peoples within a nation state and peacebuilding in such contexts. The following rationales are noteworthy for choosing the CHT as a case study:

Unique Socio-political Context: The CHT region is home to the Jumma people, comprising various indigenous communities. Conflicts in the CHT have emerged from complex historical, social, and political factors related to land rights, cultural identity, and self-determination struggles.

Cost of War and Military Operations: The conflict and associated violence in the CHT have resulted in significant casualties and a high cost of war, including loss of lives and economic resources spent on military operations, rehabilitation, and reconstruction.

Lessons for Peacebuilding: Studying the CHT region offers valuable insights into peacebuilding efforts in similar contexts. Significant efforts have been made in the region to resolve the conflict, such as the signing of the Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord in 1997. Analysing the successes, challenges, and shortcomings of these peacebuilding initiatives can provide valuable lessons for other regions facing ethnic conflicts and striving for sustainable peace.

Relevance: The CHT case study is relevant to any place across the globe where similar conflicts occur in diverse ethnic compositions. Many countries face challenges related to recognizing and protecting indigenous rights but arguably more so in the global

south. Examining the CHT case can offer insights for policymakers, academics, and practitioners in addressing conflicts rooted in identity, land rights, and autonomy.

Potential for International Collaboration: Despite receiving less international attention compared to other high-profile conflicts, the CHT conflict presents an opportunity for international collaboration and support. Engaging with the CHT case study can facilitate partnerships between local stakeholders, governments, international organizations, and researchers, aiming to collectively address the challenges and work towards achieving the difficult goal of sustainable peace.

The comprehensive process stated above and in the following sections provided support and justification for selecting the CHT as a case study of a conflict-affected environment for the doctoral research conducted by the primary author of this paper which was successfully completed in 2022 at the University of New England, Australia (Siddiqui, 2022).

3. Background of Systematic Review and its Importance

In the early 1970s the systematic review was initiated in medical research focusing on measuring the effectiveness of health care interventions (Cochrane, 1972). Now it is a pervasive approach utilized across disciplines from the natural sciences through to those concerned with the environment, health, education, and also the social sciences generally (Gough et al., 2017). Oakley (2011) credits Wootton and Miller's (1959) *Social Science & Social Pathology* as the first systematic review. Cochrane's (1972) sister initiative, the Campbell Collaboration – established in 2000 – influenced researchers and academics in the social sciences through its series of systematic review papers covering social welfare, criminology, judicature, education and development aid (Collaboration, 2014; Tugwell et al., 2010) (Farrington & Petrosino, 2001). This paper introduces a systematic review (1997-2019) for the first time, to the best of our knowledge, to peace studies literature, and more particularly, to that concerned with peacebuilding.

The importance of a systematic review lies in this: it endeavours to produce a comprehensive, unbiased, and clear assessment of the existing theories, research works, and world views involved in and constitutive of peacebuilding literature in a way simply unavailable to and through random websites search and manual library cataloguing (Mallett, Hagen-Zanker, Slater, & Duvendack, 2012). The systematic review protocol prevents researchers from an arbitrary literature selection. To this end the present study utilized two premier online databases described below.

Methodological Approach: Search terms and selection of articles

Two social science premier databases – ProQuest and EBSCOhost – were used for scholarly journal articles published in English between 1 January 1997 and 1 August 2019. The included papers deployed post-conflict peacebuilding terminologies and theories –post-liberal hybrid peace, indigeneity, peace infrastructure and positive peace – and provided a methodological account for their research. We utilized ProQuest's Politics and Policy and Applied Social Sciences Index and Abstracts (ASSIA) thesauruses to list search terms,

synonyms, and alternate spelling, for the key words and terms. For crosschecking search results yielded by the databases, the review utilized Google Scholar's advanced search option. This strategy substantiated the results produced by the principal databases.

The objective of the review was to investigate the extent to which the post-accord hybrid peacebuilding in the CHT acknowledges and correlates with positive peace, peace infrastructure and indigeneity; and to give the review a clear focus and clearly delineate an uncontroversial subject-area through thesaurus and keyword searches for the key concepts of peace infrastructure, positive peace, indigeneity, hybrid peace(building) were delineated in the context of post-Accord peacebuilding activities in the Chittagong Hill Tracts of Bangladesh. These terms were combined to identify peer reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings and other relevant resources including book chapters. In Figure II., which was developed through adoptions of Deakin University Library's Search Planner, provides the detailed landscape of the search plan and strategy.

Following strict criteria, we found 43 eligible refereed journal articles among 3076 – i.e., ProQuest 1547, EBSCOhost 928, and Google Scholar 601 – from 28 different journals for systematic and critical appraisal. The adapted Prisma (Liberati et al., 2009) diagram displays the overall procedure as to how we obtained the 43 selected articles (See Figure II).

Figure II. PRISMA Flow Diagram (Liberati et al., 2009) Adapted for the Study

This use of particular inclusion and exclusion criteria ensure the review stage remains focused on its objectives and reduces the potential for arbitrary selection and hence minimizes bias. These criteria help researchers make decisions about which studies to include or exclude from their review based on predetermined and transparent criteria

following strict protocol to mainly consider clarity and transparency, relevance, reproducibility, and consistency across studies: (Dyba, Dingsoyr, & Hanssen, 2007).

Analysis of Review Data

The selected articles were interpreted and analysed both quantitatively and qualitatively. The qualitative data interpretation followed Thematic Analysis. This approach guides us on developing patterns or "themes" (Boyatzis, 1998). In doing so, we developed a four-stage sequential procedure with some adoptions (Britten, Jones, Murphy, & Stacy, 1995; Cooper et al., 2002). First, all the selected 43 articles were read independently. Second, we identified the crucial arguments under the four major themes. Third, based on memos and nodes of NVivo12 software, we identified and analysed the causes behind peacebuilding failure, and developed a root cause policy framework. We analysed the quantitative data using IBM SPSS Statistics 25 and Microsoft XL 2013.

Boolean Fixing: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

A systematic review depends on strict boundary setting determined and maintained through inclusion and exclusion criteria. The first parameter to make appropriate searches involves Boolean conditions – e.g., AND / OR – which check for each keyword (Sayers, 2008). Our study deploys three independent variables, one dependent variable, and the very specific context that of Bangladesh’s conflict-ravaged region Chittagong Hill Tract (CHT). The search strategy included the following two-pronged principles (See Table 1):

Table I. Mapping search plan for the research topic

Criteria	Concept 1	and	Concept 2	and	Concept 3	and	Concept 4	and	Concept 5
List all key words/terms as stated in your topic description above	Peace infrastructure	→	Positive peace	→	Indigeneity	→	hybrid peacebuilding	→	Chittagong Hill Tracts
List search terms using truncation* and wildcards?	OR ↓ infrastructure s for peace; I4P		OR ↓ structural violence; negative peace; indirect violence;		OR ↓ Adivasi		OR ↓ post- accord peacebuild ing; post- conflict peace- building		OR ↓ CHT
List synonyms, alternate spelling, language, etc.	OR ↓ Armistice; Truce; Ceasefire; cease-fire		OR ↓		OR ↓ indigenous peacebuilding; indigenous peace		OR ↓ Peacebuild ing; hybrid peace; peace hybridity; peacebuild ing hybrid peace- building		OR ↓ Bangladesh BD
List words derived from available thesaurus	OR ↓ peace agreement; peace treaty; peace accord		OR ↓ absence of war; direct violence		OR ↓ local turn; peace from below; local peace;		OR ↓ liberal peace liberal; liberal peacebuild ing		OR ↓ West Bengal; East Pakistan

a) when any of the four concepts (peace infrastructure, indigeneity and positive peace, hybrid peacebuilding) appeared in the context of Bangladesh's post-accord Chittagong Hill Tracts; Or

b) hybrid peace(building) connecting to at least one of the three independent variables from anywhere across the world.

It offers several advantages over traditional literature reviews. Boolean fixing, with its use of logical operators, enhances systematic reviews by providing precision, standardization, reproducibility, time efficiency, bias minimization, comprehensive coverage, and improved search precision (Littell, Corcoran, & Pillai, 2008). It enables us to define specific criteria, streamline the search process, save time, reduce bias, ensure reproducibility, and retrieve a more targeted set of relevant documents. In contrast, systematic literature reviews employ a methodological approach with predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, rigorous search strategies, and systematic data synthesis methods. This approach aims to minimize bias, enhance transparency, ensure comprehensive coverage, and provide a more objective and reliable synthesis of the available evidence. Systematic reviews are considered a more robust and trustworthy method for evidence synthesis, providing a solid foundation for evidence-based decision-making and further research. Bias and arbitrariness in traditional literature reviews are problematic because they can lead to an incomplete and skewed understanding of the topic. This limits the validity and reliability of the review findings, potentially influencing decision-making, policy development, and further research directions based on flawed or biased interpretations (Shamseer et al., 2015).

4. Indigeneity, Peace Infrastructure, Positive Peace, and Hybrid Peace

The articles we selected for review highlight the importance of considering indigenous perspectives, engaging in locally embedded peacebuilding strategies, pursuing positive peace, and navigating the complexities of hybrid peace. Critics raise concerns about the perpetuation of liberal and universalist values within hybrid peace approaches.

INDIGENEITY, as a term in post-conflict peacebuilding theory and practice, is a relatively new phenomenon (the term "indigeneity" is not yet found in the Oxford English Dictionary.) It is the near-synonym of "aboriginality" and similarly refers to a certain group of peoples living, existing, or possessing land to which they belong "naturally" (Dictionary, 1989; Waldron, 2003). There are some explanations of how the term "indigenous" is used in various identity and conflict contexts:

Identity Context: In the identity context, "indigenous" refers to groups that have a historical (first nation) connection to a specific land area or place. For example, the Maori people of New Zealand are considered indigenous as they are the original inhabitants of the land and have a distinct language and cultural heritage that sets them apart from the European settlers (Durie, 2005).

Land Rights Context: In the context of land rights, "indigenous" is used to recognize communities' traditional and ancestral connections to specific territories. For instance, the

Native American tribes in the United States, such as the Navajo Nation, assert their indigenous status to assert their rights to ancestral lands and natural resources (Ambo and Beardall, 2023).

Conflict Context: In conflict contexts, "indigenous" is used to describe communities facing challenges and conflicts related to their identity, land, and rights. One example is the conflict involving the Mapuche people in Chile and Argentina. The Mapuche are an indigenous community that has faced historical marginalization and struggles for recognition of their rights, including land rights and cultural autonomy (Hadad, Palmisano and Wahren, 2021).

Self-Determination Context: In the context of self-determination, "indigenous" refers to communities seeking the right to govern themselves and make decisions about their own affairs. The Sámi people in northern Europe, including parts of Norway, Sweden, Finland, and Russia, are an example of an indigenous community striving for self-determination, including the preservation of their language, culture, and reindeer-herding traditions (Grey, and Kuokkanen, 2020).

It is important to note that these examples provide a glimpse into how the term "indigenous" is used in different contexts, but the specific meanings and applications may vary depending on the region and specific cultural context. However, the importance of accommodating 'local turn' – e.g., indigenous issues and local traits – in recent decades was recommended greatly to improve the climate of the inflicted environments. In fact, the dichotomy between indigeneity (indigenous pluralities) and nation, state and peace-building is arguably a natural fit in many fragile cases at least where defiant indigeneity has been forced to cease (e.g., Brett, 2013; Mac Ginty, 2008; Roberts, 2008; Tolulope & Muthoni, 2017; Werner, 2010) .

PEACE INFRASTRUCTURE, like indigeneity, is an emerging concept in the peacebuilding literature and post-conflict policy debate (Kovács, 2020). John Paul Lederach introduced the concept, emphasising locally embedded peacebuilding strategies in the context of a dynamic interplay and interdependence between the local and international (Lederach, 1997, p. xvi). Lederach stressed a comprehensive peace formation strategy rather than a mere peacebuilding strategy, where the former is alive and sensitive to local political realities, so as to contextual socio-cultural and historical traits, norms, identities, and resources, though always mediated in and through accepted "international norms" (Richmond, 2013). An example or instance of such peace infrastructure is the South African post-National Peace Accord (NPA). This was a comprehensive peace infrastructure approach where 27 parties, 11 regional peace committees and 260 local peace entities, agreed to sign the NPA (1991), and it helped defuse the violence associated with apartheid (Van Tongeren, Ojielo, Brand-Jacobsen, McCandless, & Tschirgi, 2012, p. 3), though Kovács (2020) in a review of the debates over peace infrastructures concluded that in practice, it is "more appropriate to talk about infrastructures for pacification, rather than infrastructures for peace" (p.11).

POSITIVE PEACE proponent Johan Galtung (1967, 1976, 1990) pioneered peace studies through his tripartite violence model. On this view peace is not merely the absence

of direct violence or war (“negative peace”), rather it means something more: ensuring a culture of justice through the reduction of both direct and indirect/structural violence (“positive peace”). With this distinction in mind, it can be seen that hybrid peace is likely to be fruitful only when it entails the emancipatory potential of positive peace (Mac Ginty & Richmond, 2016). On this basis we could say that the peace-building process in Bosnia and Herzegovina was not successful since it has not achieved a broadly defined positive peace. Proponents of positive peace argue that international peace-building policies have typically been formulated in terms of negative peace (cessation of violent conflict), while fully realized, positive peace depends on reducing structural violence to ensure that the generally reliable social justice contributes to a durable peace.

PEACE HYBRIDITY as a concept centre on the interplay between international intervention and its norms and domestic politics of peace governance, and public mobilization (Hoglund & Orjuela, 2012). The central principles of liberal universalist peacebuilding centre on freedom of the individual, representativeness of government, and constitutional restrictions on arbitrary power (Paris, 2010), and because of its universalist value certainty, it inevitably tends to downplay or pass over recognizing the dignity, power, and local realities. Consequently, autonomy of the local, for the local becomes secondary and subsidiary to the universal (Donais, 2012). Hence, the central argument of hybrid peace refers to a post-conflict approach that combines both traditional peacebuilding practices and external interventions to address complex and diverse conflict dynamics (Mac Ginty, 2010).

Liberal peace interventions may be suitable for full scale western corporate integration into increasingly monopolistic global capitalism, but that “suitability” will be and typically is a matter of the forced intrusion and domination of liberal norms at the expense of local norms and outlooks. The Agenda for Peace (Boutros-Ghali, 1992) and, subsequently, Responsibility to Protect (Evans & Sahnoun, 2001) brought the ‘local turn’ into peacebuilding theory and practice. But the local may be there in different guises. Following Duffield (1996), Richmond (2006) re-examined post-civil war conditions, coming up with the idea of ‘victor’s peace’ – a peace that is synonymous to the victor’s benefit and that which rests on military victory, hegemony or domination. Richmond argues that creating an institutional peace, and civil society building, are indeed important, but they are often overshadowed by the assumption that “basic security” can exist prior to an institutional, constitutional, and civil peace. Along these lines, and echoing Galtung (1967), ‘hybrid peace’ has been classified into two broader types: positive hybrid peace and negative hybrid peace (Richmond, 2015). Richmond distinguishes between the two in this way:

While a negative hybrid peace may represent the outsourcing of power and norms from the international to the state or society, a more positive hybrid form would be representative of a contextually rooted process through which broader political and social injustice is addressed, across local and international scales (Richmond, 2015, p. 51).

Many recent peacebuilding studies that are sceptical of traditional liberal universalist peacebuilding because of its value certainty and top-down statist approach (e.g., Chandler, 2014a; Lederach, 1995; Lederach, 1997; Paffenholz, 2015; Richmond & Mitchell, 2011) have called for a ‘local turn,’ with the aim of transcending traditionally conceived liberal peace for a post-liberal hybrid peace assumed to encompass local peacemakers, traditional

indigenous culture, and the everyday experience(s) of the local population within conflict-affected environments (Belloni, 2012; Peterson, 2012).

Such a hybrid juncture of peace, aimed at melding local patterns of peacebuilding to and into universalist norms, has attracted criticism of its own (ironically, given its aims and claims, quite often such criticism has emerged from representatives of 'the local'), as for instance in Alonso (2005) for whom – just because its basic value structure remains squarely liberal and universalist – 'hybridity is not inherently emancipatory in the post-colonial reality' (p. 40), but simply a more hypocritically articulated version that tends (to the extent it works at all (Nadarajah & Rampton, 2015)) to create its own kind of 'comprador' class that is both of the local, and – on the deepest value (and often financial) level – committedly liberal and universalist (Prabhu, 2012).

5. Findings and Discussion

This section considers peacebuilding literature as it relates to peace infrastructure, positive peace, and indigeneity in the context of the emerging concern for a post-liberal hybrid peace(building) discourse.

Peacebuilding Literature: Theoretical and Epistemic Trends

The following Figure III(A) maps the increase of indigenous peacebuilding literature followed by Positive Peace, and Peace Infrastructure respectively within the domain of peace hybridity. A systematic review was conducted in 2019, selecting 43 articles published between 2004 and 2019 (Siddiqui, 2022). This selection indicates the use of a structured approach to ensure objectivity and thoroughness in the article selection process. The analysis of these articles played a significant role in examining the intersection between Peace Infrastructures and various themes, including Positive Peace and Indigeneity, thereby establishing connections to Hybrid Peace. Hybrid Peace in this paper refers to peacebuilding approaches that conflate peace infrastructure, positive peace, and indigeneity with modern liberal strategies to address prevailing conflicts and negotiate a sustainable peace. The distribution of articles across these themes provides insights into the prominence of each theme within the selected literature.

Based on the provided data set, among the selected 43 articles, 8 specifically highlight the theme of Peace Infrastructures. This suggests that this particular theme is less prevalent compared to others in the dataset. 11 articles focus on the theme of Positive Peace which refers to the presence of social, political, and economic conditions that contribute to sustainable peace. The largest theme in the dataset is Indigeneity, with 25 articles which indicates that the majority of the selected articles revolve around issues related to indigenous populations and their relationship with peacebuilding and peace infrastructures.

Figure III. Growing trend of peacebuilding research (A) and Distribution of major peacebuilding themes (B) between 1997-2019 (n=43)

Based on Figure III (B), the analysis of the selected articles on hybrid peacebuilding demonstrates the growing importance of this literature over time. While the majority of the articles were published in 2012, 2017, and 2018, with 14%, 16%, and 16% respectively, it is evident that the subject has gained significant attention and scholarly interest. The distribution of publications across multiple years highlights the sustained relevance of hybrid peacebuilding as a field of study. This indicates that scholars and researchers have continued to explore and delve deeper into the complexities and nuances of hybrid peacebuilding beyond its initial emergence in academic discourse. The fact that 9% of the selected articles were published in 2015 also indicates a noteworthy contribution to the growing body of hybrid peacebuilding literature. This suggests that the field was already gaining traction and recognition within the academic community at that time. Furthermore, the remaining 20% of articles published in 2004, 2006, 2009, 2014, 2016, and 2019 indicate that hybrid peacebuilding literature has been steadily expanding over a broader time frame.

This suggests a sustained interest and an ongoing exploration of the subject, with researchers looking back to earlier years and forward to recent developments. The increasing importance of hybrid peacebuilding literature can be attributed to several factors. First, a response to the complex and multifaceted nature of contemporary conflicts. Second, the growing recognition that peacebuilding efforts must adapt to changing conflict dynamics has fuelled interest in hybrid approaches. Third, the rise of non-state actors, including insurgent groups, criminal organizations, and transnational networks, has further emphasized the need for hybrid approaches in peacebuilding. Finally, the hybrid peacebuilding literature has likely benefited from increased attention and funding for research and practice in the broader field of peacebuilding and conflict resolution. As the importance of preventing and resolving conflicts has gained recognition on the global stage, scholars and practitioners have sought to develop more comprehensive and effective approaches, contributing to the growth of hybrid peacebuilding literature. The increasing attention to hybrid approaches reflects the need to adapt to the complex and evolving nature of conflicts in the contemporary world.

It is often claimed (e.g., Gelot, 2018) that the pursuit of positive peace in peace research has been marginalized because Liberal Peace, with its determined top-down focus and consequent disregard for local institutional and cultural realities is concerned only with an imposed negative peace, our study reveals this is at most only a very partial truth. About 23% of selected papers (10) directly focused on 'positive peace,' with 4 of those utilizing it as the analytical framework for studies conducted on Bosnia and Herzegovina, while six papers discussed positive peace issues from a general descriptive perspective. In fact, Galtung's argument for reducing or eliminating structural violence (Galtung, 1969), which is often used as antonymous to promoting positive peace, appeared in another 12% (5) papers, which means altogether that 35% of the papers discussed and/or adopted the notion of positive peace.

6. Methods, Gaps and Cases Underpinned in the Reviewed Articles

Ideally, a systematic review helps us identify research gap(s) in the literature (Petticrew & Roberts, 2008). Wallis and Richmond (2017), in their methodical paper on peacebuilding, argued that the clash between the presumed universalism of liberal individualism and the realities of local relatedness resulted, most productively, with a concern for a hybrid peacebuilding that saw the entire project/process as more complex and less certain than often assumed. They argued for a broadly comprehended and contextually mediated inclusive peacebuilding architecture grounded in a truly multi-disciplinary conversation. It is in this context that we find mentioned the need for a 'local turn' (the necessity of listening to the grassroots level of peacebuilding where the community of people live), but for all these discussions of importance placed on the local, we found that most of the studies (more than 67%) worked off secondary (personal interview to semi-structured interviews, snowballing interviews, seminars, workshops, and focus group discussions (FGD)).

Though this review focuses on hybrid peace and its associates – positive peace, indigeneity/indigenous peace, and peace infrastructure – we find the continuing dominance of liberal peace clear. For example, Mac Ginty (2010) uses liberal/liberalism or liberal peacebuilding term 169 times and hybrid/hybridity 81 times in an article titled Hybrid peace: The interaction between top-down and bottom-up peace. Moreover, one essay did not mention 'hybrid' in its abstract – though it used the term 'liberal' six times – despite its title¹ (Becoming Liberal, Unbecoming Liberalism: Liberal-Local Hybridity via the Everyday as a Response to the Paradoxes of Liberal Peacebuilding) (see, Richmond, 2009).

Showcasing Geographic Contexts Used in the Reviewed Papers

In terms of geographical distribution, the cases in the reviewed literature ranged from South and South-East Asia to southeastern Europe, to Africa to Central and South America. Continentally, most of the cases were from Africa – Rwanda, Uganda, and Mozambique (Werner, 2010) and (Wilén, 2012); South Sudan (Tolulope & Muthoni, 2017); Kosovo (Visoka & Richmond, 2017); Ghana, South Africa, Kenya, Sudan' South Kordofan, DRC's

¹ Article titled "Becoming Liberal, Unbecoming Liberalism: Liberal-Local Hybridity via the Everyday as a Response to the Paradoxes of Liberal Peacebuilding" and Keywords comprised of liberal peace; everyday; empathy; local-liberal; hybridity.

North Kivu, North Kivu, North Kivu and Ituri, Burundi, Nigeria, Uganda (Irene, 2018); Burundi (Maphosa, 2013). Indeed, Africa all alone hosts seven (out of 13) peacekeeping operations led by the UN's Department of Peace Operations (of the remaining operations, six are in European Kosovo, four are in the Middle East, and one on India and Pakistan's disputed border Jammu and Kashmir (see all operations in details: Peacekeeping, 2020).

When it comes to South-East Asia, Cambodia is covered by Roberts (2008) and Simangan (2018); Timor-Leste by Wallis (2017) and Simangan (2017); and Sri Lanka by three separate papers – i.e., Laffey and Nadarajah (2012), Høglund and Orjuela (2012) and Jirasinghe (2018). Two papers by Brett (2013) and one by Wolff (2015) looked at the Central (and South) American states, Guatemala, and Bolivia respectively. While Kříž and Čermák (2014) focused on Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Forde (2019) looked at Bosnia and Herzegovina's Mostar. There were several cross-regional multiple case study papers. Guyana, Bolivia, Ghana, Kenya, and Timor-Leste are examined by Kumar and De la Haye (2012); Timor-Leste and the Solomon Islands by Oliver P Richmond (2009); Bosnia and Herzegovina, Afghanistan, Sierra Leone by Mac Ginty (2010); and Bosnia and Herzegovina, Iraq, Afghanistan, and Lebanon by Jarstad and Belloni (2012). On the other hand, 44% (19) papers did not identify any specific geographical context of peacebuilding intervention, but spoke generally of theoretical, conceptual and review paradigms, occasionally referring to particular contexts for the purpose of developing more general concerns.

A significant portion of the reviewed literature focuses on theoretical, conceptual, and review paradigms, without specifying a specific geographical context for peacebuilding interventions. The analysis reveals that a diverse range of geographical locations are covered in the literature on hybrid peacebuilding, with a predominant focus on Africa. This justifies the selection of the CHT case for this study which is an important conflict that has continued for some time in South Asia. However, the inclusion of discussions of various regions reflects the global interest and applicability of hybrid peacebuilding approaches in addressing complex conflicts and negotiating approaches to building sustainable peace.

Methodological Challenges: A posteriori demonstration

We found, an overwhelming dependency on qualitative and secondary information over a concern for primary data; there is a glaring dearth of quantitative data and analyses. A clustered bar chart (Figure IV.) compares the range of methods, including data collection, found in the 43 papers reviewed. As Figure IV demonstrates, one paper out of 43 (2%) was determinedly quantitative – a mixed-methods approach aimed at evaluating the peacebuilding implementation outcomes for Burundi. Conversely, all the papers, even the single quantitative paper, were grounded on qualitative paradigms and subjective interpretations. Of them 67% (29) used secondary sources, while only 33% (14) collected and analysed primary data. Some 56% (24) followed case study design (single case 40%, multiple case 16%).

We found no instances or examples of systematic sampling for the purpose of measuring peacebuilding implementation output (see Figure IV.). And while Maphosa

(2013) employed an ‘exploratory mixed-method design’ to evaluate community-based peacebuilding interventions at the individual and village level in conflict-affected Burundi, he did not follow probability sampling in selecting his 62 local level participants.

Figure IV. Distribution of methodological juncture of peacebuilding literature

In summary, the comparison of data in the selected papers highlights a predominant preference for qualitative research methods, particularly single case studies, and a reliance on secondary data. The prevalence of qualitative methods suggests a focus on understanding context, capturing rich narratives, and exploring subjective aspects. However, the moderate usage of primary data collection methods indicates a balanced approach to gathering firsthand information. The limited utilization of quantitative and mixed-methods implies a lesser emphasis on statistical analysis and a preference for qualitative insights in these studies. In order to rediscover indigenous peace-making perspectives against the explicit universalism of liberal peace, and the less explicit but just as real universalism of what has been determined as hybrid peace (Werner, 2010), we must think creatively about methodological issues in conflict-affected societies (Maphosa, 2013), for only then might we reliably generate sound empirical evidence (Paffenholz, 2015), and so move from constructivist to critical engagements with peacebuilding (Wallis & Richmond, 2017).

Locally-ingrained Context-specific Indigenous Peace Infrastructure

One thing our review reveals is that the emphasis on the ‘local’/ ‘international’ binary, either in the bluntly hegemonic sense of top-down liberal universalism, or the equally, but less obvious, universalism of hybridity, has had the unfortunate consequence of occluding one crucial residual in the post-colonial era – the ‘internal colonial’ framework that ensued a nationalism based on territoriality. By assuming uncritically realities of post-colonial ‘nationhood,’ peripheral ‘regionhood’ has fallen from view. It has done so because this nationhood focus sees international liberal peace vendors place the central metropole (and its elites) at the heart of peacebuilding, assuming they are responsible for resolving more local (and often more real) regional discontents. Such approaches threaten an unwitting “liberal colonialism” as argued by Mazower (2013) and Richmond (2018). Many ‘fringes’ (that is, regional peripheries to the metropole, as with the CHT in Bangladesh, Kashmir in India and Pakistan, Mostar in Bosnia, and Herzegovina) have been ignored (or attended to far less) by peacebuilding scholars compared to those of centrally fragile states such as in Bolivia, Guatemala, Sudan etc. Though critical peace scholars are often devoted to emancipatory ideas of peace like ‘indigenous peacebuilding,’ ‘everyday’ ‘local peace’ and

so on (Chandler, 2014a; Mac Ginty, 2008; Richmond & Mitchell, 2011; Richmond, 2009), peripheral cases are not as conspicuous in the literature.

Each conflict-affected region or state has its own context-specific cultural setting and therefore its own practical domain and characteristic practices. And as Mac Ginty, Joshi, and Lee (2019) show, of the 34 post-Cold postaccord peacebuilding projects, those (as, for example in Rwanda, Uganda, and Mozambique) that have drawn on traditional or indigenous forms of conflict resolution might not strictly honour the standards of liberal peace, but they do tend to have more local legitimacy and force (Mac Ginty, 2010). The obvious lesson is that peacebuilding efforts must be tailored in response to specific contexts and types of conflict (Werner, 2010). For instance, in Rwanda, the gacaca courts that locally trusted people dedicated to ensuring transitional justice in the wake of Rwanda genocide organized and ran constitute a hybrid form of peacebuilding that brings traditional structures together with the 'international norms' of liberal peace in a way that has some capacity to allow flexible dialogue (Werner, 2010, p. 65). This, and other examples like it, prompt many critical peace scholars (Bargues-Pedreny & Pol, 2014; Bargaés-Pedreny, 2015; Bose & Motwani, 2014; Jarstad & Belloni, 2012) to argue in favour of unfolding local possibilities and the potential for this kind of effort to produce a locally-ingrained version of peace.

Hybridity, does not mean, of itself, that liberal universalism has lost its hegemonic sway – to the contrary, many, such as Werner, see it as developing and deepening the impact of such universalism through a certain local context sensitivity. But it is not far from recognition of hybridity as a useful tool in the liberal universalist peace armoury, to a suspicion that liberal universalism might have gone astray here from the start. For the very recognition of hybridity reveals that liberal peace is not only the mere absence of war or violent conflict and presence of electoral democratic practices, but demands, and rests upon, and lives in and through localized rights, traditions, customary laws, needs and identity. Given this, of course, any genuine reflective concern for peacebuilding must allow these factors their own voice and relative autonomy. It is a mark of the continuing hold of liberal universalism here such that so often this turn to the local is rebuffed as romantic, relativist, particularistic, and anti-democratic, and could be seen as contributing to perceptions of anti-development (Mac Ginty & Richmond, 2013, p. 764).

Our systematic literature review has convinced us to say that conflict-afflicted environments demand and deserve a very context-specific peace formation that must be endogenously contextualized: neither conventional liberal universalist peacebuilding, nor a 'hybridity' dominated by such liberal peace commitments are sufficient as approaches to sustaining peace. "Good enough" peacebuilding may and indeed, typically, will involve a genuine and non-condescending sensitivity to local context and culture, and thereby genuinely consider the local people(s) wishes. It means, acknowledging and demanding strong and inclusive national ownership and leadership when it comes to peacebuilding endeavours, but doing so in a way that enables a willingness to shape and revise aims, methods, and procedures in the light of context-specific factors understood as essential to the meaning of peace and the way(s) towards achieving it.

As with the emergence in the literature of 'indigeneity,' the call for a local turn in conflict resolution and reconciliation has been growing (Mac Ginty, 2008). Indigeneity

provides an opportunity for acknowledging that calls for self-governance by the subjects of peacebuilding efforts is a context-driven demand to be answered in context-sensitive and specific terms (Bargués-Pedreny & Randazzo, 2018). Roberts (2008) argues, for “negotiated hybridity” through a process of consensus-building. But, as we have seen, if such consensus-building is dominated by the top-down paradigm implicit to liberal universalism then any such ‘consensus’ is predetermined by non-local actors and ideas. Here we make our own proposal for indigenous peace infrastructure(s) – e.g., the setting up of a Ministry of Indigenous Peace – run by indigenous representatives as instrumental to successful peace formation. What we are after is a (local) culture of dialogue, tolerance, solidarity and understanding, democratic participation, free information flow, DDR, human dignity, and equality and equity. In practice, such a ministry would be crucial to directing government policy towards the nonviolent resolution of conflict and to the quest for peace by peaceful means, and be responsible for the development, co-ordination, implementation, monitoring and evaluating of the peace process. Such a ministerial approach would help promote restorative justice as well as a wider understanding of peace, but to do so requires a state government that is open and willing to participate in such a cooperative initiative with local indigenous peoples. The justification for employing a locally-ingrained peacebuilding approach in the Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT) in Bangladesh has furthermore been supported by the findings of a survey conducted in the region based on a mixed quantitative cum qualitative research methodology (Siddiqui, Jenkins, & Ahmed, 2023). The results of the survey are discussed in depth in the first author’s PhD thesis (Siddiqui, 2022).

7. Conclusion

Liberal peace is – despite its claims to be about ‘toleration’ – a universalist project that, of its nature, downplays the autonomy and ethical-political capacities of local indigenous communities. The Eurocentric colonial model is, from the local point of view a matter of structural violence that works against positive peace formation (Bentley, Sullivan, & Wilson, 2017). The literature reviewed presented no significant success story of liberal and post-liberal hybrid peacebuilding efforts. Similarly, no significant policy recommendations are to be found in the literature reviewed, that is because of a clear lack of research evidence emerging in the first decade of the 21st Century, ‘for a local turn.’ While the discussion in our paper surely contributes an encouraging advance, the trouble is that this ‘local turn’ has not been fully or adequately defined and explained from a critical point of view, nor has it been subject to well-defined quantitative analyses. The challenge of hybrid peace arises when indigeneity faces threats from modernity and the dominant paradigm of liberal peacebuilding. To preserve and celebrate indigenous diversity, it becomes essential to reduce the dominance of liberal and hybrid peacebuilding approaches, and instead embrace context-specific, inclusive strategies that respect indigenous knowledge, practices, and identities, thus fostering sustainable and culturally sensitive peace.

Conflict of Interest Declaration: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

8. References

1. Alonso, A. M. (2005). Territorializing the nation and 'integrating the Indian': 'Mestizaje' in Mexican official discourses and public culture. *Sovereign bodies: Citizens, migrants, and states in the postcolonial world*, 39-60.
2. Ambo, T., & Rocha Beardall, T. (2023). Performance or Progress? The Physical and Rhetorical Removal of
3. Indigenous Peoples in Settler Land Acknowledgments at Land-Grab Universities. *American Educational Research Journal*, 60(1), 103-140.
4. Armstrong, R., Hall, B. J., Doyle, J., & Waters, E. (2011). 'Scoping the scope' of a cochrane review. *Journal of Public Health*, 33(1), 147-150. doi:10.1093/pubmed/fdr015
5. Badiuzzaman, M., & Murshed, S. M. (2015). Conflict and livelihood decisions in the Chittagong Hill
6. Tracts of Bangladesh. *Poverty reduction policies and practices in developing Asia*, 145-162.
7. Bagues-Pedreny, & Pol, B. P. (2014). Embracing difference and the deferral of self-government: a critical analysis of the framing and practice of contemporary peace building. University of Westminster,
8. Bagues-Pedreny, P. (2015). Conceptualising Local Ownership as 'Reflexive Cooperation': The Deferral of Self-government to Protect 'Unequal' Humans?
9. Bagues-Pedreny, P., & Randazzo, E. (2018). Hybrid peace revisited: an opportunity for considering self-governance? *Third World Quarterly*, 39(8), 1543-1560.
10. Belloni, R. (2012). Hybrid peace governance: Its emergence and significance. *Global Governance*, 18, 21.
11. Bentley, D., Sullivan, S., & Wilson, K. (2017). British Colonialism: Perpetuating Structural Violence through Perceptual Misunderstandings in Canada *Peace Research*, 49(2), 61-78, 143, 145. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com.ezproxy.une.edu.au/docview/2236679078?accountid=17227>
12. Bose, S., & Motwani, N. (2014). The Limits of 'Hybrid Governance' in Afghanistan. *Strategic Analysis*, 38(4), 416-426.
13. Boutellis, A. (2017). The threat of US cuts: helping peacekeeping help itself? Retrieved from <https://theglobalobservatory.org/2017/03/peacekeeping-funding-united-states-trump-security-council/>
14. Boutros-Ghali, B. (1992). An agenda for peace: Preventive diplomacy, peacemaking and peace-keeping. *International Relations*, 11(3), 201-218.
15. Boyatzis, R. E. (1998). Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development: sage.
16. Brett, R. (2013). Peace stillborn? Guatemala's liberal peace and the indigenous movement. *Peacebuilding*, 1(2), 222-238.
17. Britten, N., Jones, R., Murphy, E., & Stacy, R. (1995). Qualitative research methods in general practice and primary care. *Family practice*, 12(1), 104-114.
18. Campbell, S., Chandler, D., & Sabaratnam, M. (2011). *A liberal peace?: the problems and practices of peacebuilding*: Zed Books Ltd.
19. Chakma, A. (2017). The Peacebuilding of the Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT), Bangladesh: Donor-Driven or Demand-Driven? *Asian Journal of Peacebuilding*, 5(2), 223-242. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=a9h&AN=126703603&site=ehost-live>
20. Chandler, D. (2014a). Resilience and the 'everyday': beyond the paradox of 'liberal peace'. *Review of International Studies*, 41(01), 27-48. doi:10.1017/s0260210513000533
21. Chandler, D. (2014b). *Statebuilding and intervention: policies, practices and paradigms*: Routledge.
22. Cochrane, A. (1972). Effectiveness and efficiency: Random reflections on health services. In: Royal Society of Medicine Press.
23. Collaboration, C. (2014). *Campbell systematic reviews: Policies and guidelines*. Campbell Systematic Reviews, 1.

24. Cooper, V., Buick, D., Horne, R., Lambert, N., Gellaitry, G., Leake, H., & Fisher, M. (2002). Perceptions of HAART among gay men who declined a treatment offer: preliminary results from an interview-based study. *AIDS care*, 14(3), 319-328.
25. De Coning, C. (2016). From peacebuilding to sustaining peace: Implications of complexity for resilience and sustainability. *Resilience*, 4(3), 166-181.
26. De Coning, C. (2018). Adaptive peacebuilding. *International Affairs*, 94(2), 301-317.
27. Dictionary, O. E. (1989). *Oxford english dictionary*. Simpson, JA & Weiner, ESC.
28. Donais, T. (2012). *Peacebuilding and local ownership: Post-conflict consensus-building*: Routledge.
29. Duffield, M. (1996). *Global Governance and the New Wars: The merging of development and security*. *African Security Review*.
30. Duffield, M. (2014). *Global governance and the new wars: The merging of development and security*: Zed Books Ltd.
31. Durie, M. (2005). Indigenous knowledge within a global knowledge system. *Higher Education Policy*, 18,
32. 301-312.
33. Evans, G. J., & Sahnoun, M. (2001). *The responsibility to protect: report of the International Commission on Intervention and State Sovereignty*: IDRC.
34. Dyba, T., Dingsoyr, T., & Hanssen, G. K. (2007, September). *Applying systematic reviews to diverse study*
35. *types: An experience report*. In *First international symposium on empirical software engineering and measurement (ESEM 2007)* (pp. 225-234). IEEE.
36. Farrington, D. P., & Petrosino, A. (2001). The Campbell collaboration crime and justice group. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 578(1), 35-49.
37. Galtung, J. (1967). *Theories of peace*. Oslo: A Synthetic Approach to Peace Thinking International Peace Research Institute, on September.
38. Galtung, J. (1969). Violence, peace, and peace research. *Journal of Peace Research*, 6(3), 167-191.
39. Galtung, J. (1976). *Peace, war and defense: Essays in peace research*: Christian Ejlertsen.
40. Galtung, J. (1990). Cultural Violence. *Journal of Peace Research*, 27(3), 291-305. doi:10.1177/0022343390027003005
41. Gelot, L. (2018). Reclaiming the Transcendence of Positive Peace Against the Violence of Post-Liberal Peace. *International Journal on World Peace*, 35(2), 27-52.
42. Gough, D., Oliver, S., & Thomas, J. (2017). *An introduction to systematic reviews*: Sage.
43. Grey, S., & Kuokkanen, R. (2020). Indigenous governance of cultural heritage: searching for alternatives to
44. co-management. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 26(10), 919-941.
45. Hadad, M. G., Palmisano, T., & Wahren, J. (2021). Socio-territorial disputes and violence on fracking land
46. in Vaca Muerta, Argentina. *Latin American Perspectives*, 48(1), 63-83.
47. Høglund, K., & Orjuela, C. (2012). Hybrid peace governance and illiberal peacebuilding in Sri Lanka. *Global Governance*, 18, 89.
48. Irene, O. F. (2018). Infrastructures for Peace: African Experience and Lesson. *Journal of African Conflicts and Peace Studies*, 4(1), 4.
49. Jarstad, A. K., & Belloni, R. (2012). Introducing hybrid peace governance: Impact and prospects of liberal peacebuilding. *Global Governance*, 18, 1.
50. Jirasinghe, R. (2018). Liberal peace and peacebuilding: global and local debates in the context of Sri Lanka. *Sri Lanka journal of social sciences*, 41(1), 01-23.
51. Kovács, B. Á. (2020). Peace Infrastructures. In *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of Peace and Conflict Studies* (pp. 1-13). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
52. Kříž, Z., & Čermák, P. (2014). Bosnia and Herzegovina between Negative and Positive Peace: View from the Local Level. *Romanian Journal of Political Science*, 14(2), 4-36. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=a9h&AN=114157156&site=ehost-live>

53. Kumar, C., & De la Haye, J. (2012). Hybrid Peacemaking: Building National "Infrastructures for Peace". *Global Governance*, 18(1), 13-20. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com.ezproxy.une.edu.au/docview/928515270?accountid=17227>
54. Laffey, M., & Nadarajah, S. (2012). The hybridity of liberal peace: States, diasporas and insecurity. *Security Dialogue*, 43(5), 403-420.
55. Lederach, J. P. (1995). *Preparing for peace: Conflict transformation across cultures*: Syracuse University Press.
56. Lederach, J. P. (1997). *Building Peace: sustainable reconciliation in divided societies*. Retrieved from Washington D. C. :
57. Liberati, A., Altman, D. G., Tetzlaff, J., Mulrow, C., Gøtzsche, P. C., Ioannidis, J. P., . . . Moher, D. (2009). The PRISMA statement for reporting systematic reviews and meta-analyses of studies that evaluate health care interventions: explanation and elaboration. *Journal of clinical epidemiology*, 62(10), e1-e34.
58. Likert, R. (1932). A technique for the measurement of attitudes. *Archives of psychology*.
59. Littell, J. H., Corcoran, J., & Pillai, V. (2008). *Systematic reviews and meta-analysis*. Oxford University Press.
60. Press.
61. Mac Ginty, R. (2008). Indigenous peace-making versus the liberal peace. *Cooperation and conflict*, 43(2), 139-163.
62. Mac Ginty, R. (2010). Hybrid peace: The interaction between top-down and bottom-up peace. *Security Dialogue*, 41(4), 391-412.
63. Mac Ginty, R., Joshi, M., & Lee, S. (2019). Liberal Peace Implementation and the Durability of Post-war Peace. *International Peacekeeping*, 1-30.
64. Mac Ginty, R., & Richmond, O. (2016). The fallacy of constructing hybrid political orders: a reappraisal of the hybrid turn in peacebuilding. *International Peacekeeping*, 23(2), 219-239.
65. Mac Ginty, R., & Richmond, O. P. (2013). The Local Turn in Peace Building: a critical agenda for peace. *Third World Quarterly*, 34(5), 763-783. doi:10.1080/01436597.2013.800750
66. Mahmoud, Y., & Makoond, A. (2017). *Sustaining Peace: What Does It Mean in Practice?*
67. Mallett, R., Hagen-Zanker, J., Slater, R., & Duvendack, M. (2012). The benefits and challenges of using systematic reviews in international development research. *Journal of development effectiveness*, 4(3), 445-455. doi:10.1080/19439342.2012.711342
68. Maphosa, S. B. (2013). Thinking creatively about methodological issues in conflict-affected societies: a primer from the field. *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development*, 8(2), 91-104.
69. Mazower, M. (2013). *No enchanted palace: the end of empire and the ideological origins of the United Nations (Vol. 1)*: Princeton University Press.
70. Nadarajah, S., & Rampton, D. (2015). The limits of hybridity and the crisis of liberal peace. *Review of International Studies*, 41(1), 49-72.
71. Oakley, A. (2011). *A critical woman: Barbara Wootton, social science and public policy in the twentieth century*: Bloomsbury Publishing.
72. Paffenholz, T. (2015). Unpacking the local turn in peacebuilding: a critical assessment towards an agenda for future research. *Third World Quarterly*, 36(5), 857-874.
73. Partha, R. S. (2020). *Life beyond the paradox: Peace, ethnic conflict, and everyday realities of*
74. Chittagong Hill Tracts, Bangladesh 1. In *The Dynamics of Conflict and Peace in Contemporary South Asia* (pp. 143-162). Routledge.
75. Panday, P. K., & Jamil, I. (2009). Conflict in the Chittagong Hill Tracts of bangladesh: an unimplemented accord and continued violence. *Asian Survey*, 49(6), 1052-1070.
76. Paris, R. (2010). Saving liberal peacebuilding. *Review of International Studies*, 36(2), 337-365. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0260210510000057>
77. *Peacekeeping*, U. N. (2020). *United Nations Peacekeeping* Retrieved from <https://peacekeeping.un.org/en/where-we-operate>
78. Peterson, J. H. (2012). A conceptual unpacking of hybridity: Accounting for notions of power, politics and progress in analyses of aid-driven interfaces. *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development*, 7(2), 9-22.

79. Petticrew, M., & Roberts, H. (2008). *Systematic reviews in the social sciences: A practical guide*: John Wiley & Sons.
80. Prabhu, A. (2012). *Hybridity: Limits, transformations, prospects*: SUNY Press.
81. Richmond, O. P. (2013). Peace Formation and Local Infrastructures for Peace. *Alternatives: Global, Local, Political*, 38(4), 271-287. doi:10.1177/0304375413512100
82. Richmond, O. P. (2015). The dilemmas of a hybrid peace: Negative or positive? *Cooperation and conflict*, 50(1), 50-68.
83. Richmond, O. P., & Mitchell, A. (2011). *Hybrid forms of peace: from everyday agency to post-liberalism*: Springer.
84. Richmond, O. P. (2006). The problem of peace: understanding the 'liberal peace'. *Conflict, Security & Development*, 6(3), 291-314.
85. Richmond, O. P. (2009). Becoming liberal, unbecoming liberalism: Liberal-local hybridity via the everyday as a response to the paradoxes of liberal peacebuilding. *Journal of intervention and statebuilding*, 3(3), 324-344.
86. Richmond, O. P. (2009). A post-liberal peace: Eireneism and the everyday. *Review of International Studies*, 35(3), 557-580.
87. Richmond, O. P. (2018). The green and the cool: Hybridity, relationality and ethnographic-biographical responses to intervention. *Mediterranean Politics*, 23(4), 479-500. doi:10.1080/13629395.2017.1338214
88. Roberts, D. (2008). Hybrid polities and indigenous pluralities: Advanced lessons in statebuilding from Cambodia. *Journal of intervention and statebuilding*, 2(1), 63-86.
89. Rosenthal, G. (2015). *The challenge of sustaining peace: Report of the Advisory Group of Experts for the*
90. 2015 review of the United Nations peacebuilding architecture.
91. Roy, R. C. K. (2000). Land rights of the indigenous peoples of the Chittagong Hill Tracts, Bangladesh (No. 99). Iwgia.
92. Roy, R. D. (2004). Challenges for juridical pluralism and customary laws of indigenous peoples: The case of the Chittagong Hill Tracts, Bangladesh. *Ariz. J. Int'l & Comp. L.*, 21, 113.
93. Sayers, A. (2008). Tips and tricks in performing a systematic review. *British Journal of General Practice*, 58(547), 136-136.
94. Shamseer, L., Moher, D., Clarke, M., Ghersi, D., Liberati, A., Petticrew, M., ... & Stewart, L. A. (2015).
95. Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. *Bmj*, 349.
96. Siddiqui, M.S.H., Jenkins, B. A. & Ahmed, E (2023). *Sequential Explanatory Mixed-Methods Research:*
97. *Adapting in the Conflict-affected Chittagong Hill Tracts of Bangladesh. Asian Journal of Peacebuilding* Vol. 11 No. 2 (2023): 1-22. doi: 10.18588/202304.00a327
98. Siddiqui, M.S.H. (2022). *Post Accord Peace: Hybrid Peacebuilding and the Diminishing Status of*
99. *Indigeneity Among Peoples of The Chittagong Hill Tracts (Unpublished PhD Thesis)*
100. Siddiqui, M. S. H. (2016). *Challenges of Implementing Peace Accord: The Case of Chittagong Hill Tracts*
101. *Peace Accord (CHTPA) in Bangladesh (Master's thesis, The University of Bergen).*
102. Simangan, D. (2017). A Detour in the Local Turn: Roadblocks in Timor-Leste's Post-Conflict Peacebuilding. *Asian Journal of Peacebuilding*, 5(2), 195-221. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=a9h&AN=126703602&site=ehost-live>
103. Simangan, D. (2018). When hybridity breeds contempt: negative hybrid peace in Cambodia. *Third World Quarterly*, 39(8), 1525-1542.
104. T Call, C., & de Coning, C. (2017). *Rising Powers and Peacebuilding: Breaking the Mold?* : Springer Nature.
105. Tolulope, A. J., & Muthoni, M. J. (2017). Indigenous approaches to peace building: examining the strategies employed by women in south Sudan. *Gender & Behaviour*, 15(3),

- 9639-9651. Retrieved from <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/gab/article/view/165576>
106. Tugwell, P., Petticrew, M., Kristjansson, E., Welch, V., Ueffing, E., Waters, E., . . . Kelly, M. P. (2010). Assessing equity in systematic reviews: realising the recommendations of the Commission on Social Determinants of Health. *Bmj*, 341, c4739.
 107. Van Tongeren, P., Ojielo, M. O., Brand-Jacobsen, K., McCandless, E., & Tschirgi, N. (2012). The Evolving Landscape of Infrastructures for Peace. *Journal of peacebuilding and development*, 7(3), 1-7.
 108. Visoka, G., & Richmond, O. (2017). After liberal peace? From failed state-building to an emancipatory peace in Kosovo. *International Studies Perspectives*, 18(1), 110-129.
 109. Waldron, J. (2003). Indigeneity-first peoples and last occupancy. *NZJPI*, 1, 55.
 110. Wallis, J. (2017). Is 'good enough' peacebuilding good enough? The potential and pitfalls of the local turn in peacebuilding in Timor-Leste. *Pacific Review*, 30(2), 251-269. doi:10.1080/09512748.2016.1220417
 111. Wallis, J., & Richmond, O. (2017). From constructivist to critical engagements with peacebuilding: implications for hybrid peace. *Third World Thematics: A TWQ Journal*, 2(4), 422-445.
 112. Werner, K. (2010). Rediscovering Indigenous Peacebuilding Techniques: The Way to Lasting Peace? *Africa Peace and Conflict Journal*, 3(2), 60-73. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=a9h&AN=119954785&site=ehost-live>
 113. Wilén, N. (2012). A Hybrid Peace through Locally Owned and Externally Financed SSR–DDR in Rwanda? *Third World Quarterly*, 33(7), 1323-1336.
 114. Wootton, B., & Miller, S. (1959). Social science & social pathology. *Social Work (1939-1970)*, 16(4), 122-126.
 115. Wright, R. W., Brand, R. A., Dunn, W., & Spindler, K. P. (2007). How to write a systematic review. *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research (1976-2007)*, 455, 23-29.

Author Contacts

Muhammad Sazzad Hossain Siddiqui is an Associate Professor in the Department of Peace and Conflict Studies at the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. He holds an MPhil in Public Administration from the University of Bergen, Norway, and a PhD in Hybrid Peacebuilding and Indigeneity Dilution from the University of New England, Australia. Email: sazzadhsiddiqui@du.ac.bd

Tony Lynch is a Senior Lecturer at University of New England (UNE), Australia. He holds a BA (Hons) from the University of Tasmania and Ph.D. from the University of Sydney, Australia. Email: alynch@une.edu.au

Bertram A Jenkins is an Adjunct Faculty of Peace Studies at the University of New England, Australia. He holds a PhD in Community Ecology from the University of New England, Australia. Email: bjenkins@une.edu.au